

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF JOB RECRUITMENT IN THE PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SECTORS OF THE NIGERIAN ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

The paper examines the state of job recruitment, as well as the socio-political contexts leading to the realities of human resources recruitment in the public and private sectors of the Nigerian economy today. The paper presents a comparative analysis of job recruitment practices in these two sectors through a critical review of available literature. The data collected were analyzed thematically, as contained in the discussion section, showing the areas of difference and similarities between the two sectors. The themes explored are the statutory obligations, modes and sources of recruitment, maintenance of equity and diversity, workforce planning and audit, entry requirements, and area of placements.

It was found that while the sectors have different approaches to setting of entry requirements, sources of recruitment, and statutory obligations, both face similar challenges in the areas of the struggle to manage and maintain diversity and equality in the workplace as well as with the ills associated with delegation of recruitment activities to specialized agencies or ministerial and extra-ministerial departments.

The paper recommends that employers of labour in Nigeria, especially the central government, should ensure principles of equity and fairness is strictly adhered to in recruitment processes especially by reviewing the Federal Character principle if it is to perform its initial focus, to carry out recruitment exercises only based on human resources needs, and to propagate employment regulations that will guarantee job security in the private sector to reduce the pressures for employment in the public sector among other recommendations.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Organizations today operate in a dynamic, rapidly evolving, and challenging environment occasioned by intense competition, globalization and the spread of information technology, economic changes, and workforce diversity. These challenges make it imperative for employers to ensure that qualified personnel is recruited to stimulate immediate and future job performances. When the right caliber of employees are recruited in the right position, it creates the atmosphere for organizational efficiency and high productivity, while hiring wrong only leads to job mismatch, unnecessary cost overhead, poor job output, and business failure. Organizations that will thrive in this dispensation will have to go beyond just having someone to do the job, but to ensure prospective candidates with requisite skills and qualifications are sufficiently attracted to fill vacant job positions in a timely manner (Robbins and Coulter, 2002; Osibanjo and Adeniji, 2013; Ekwoaba, Ikeije and Ufoma, 2015; Onwe, Abah and Nwokwu, 2015).

Recruitment and selection is a staffing activity that involves identifying, attracting, hiring, and retaining persons with the needed knowledge, skills, and abilities to realize organizational goals (Anyim *et al.*, 2012; Osemeke, 2012; Pangemanan, 2015). Recruitment is one of the crucial tasks of modern management and lies at the heart of the problems of human resources management. Thus, recruitment and selection should be handled with utmost caution so as to efficiently and effectively achieve organizational goals and objectives. In Nigeria however, it is perceived that the recruitment process is to a large extent menaced by inequity and obscurity, making it difficult if not impossible to recruit the best-qualified applicants for available jobs. This is evident in the poor organizational performances in Nigeria. The discerned problems of recruitment in Nigeria have been attributed to factors such as inadequate and deficient standards for evaluating job candidates, sources of locating the potential applicants, transparency, and independence of recruiting authorities, and the administrative machinery for determination of qualifications (Obisi, 2006; Briggs, 2017).

The paper aims to pinpoint contributory factors to the inadequacies of the exercise in the Nigerian public and private sectors by conducting a comparative analysis of both sectors through a review of available literature. The paper goes further to recommend possible solutions to the identified lapses.

2. CONCEPTUAL, LEGAL & SOCIO-POLITICAL FRAMEWORK: Human Resources Recruitment, Public and Private Sector in Nigeria

2.1 Overview of Human Resources Recruitment

The notion that recruitment is the foundation upon which organizational performance is built continues to gain traction. The efficiency and effectiveness of any organization are dependent on the quality of workforce it has recruited to carry out its operations and it has become evident that ineffective recruitment practices come with a lot of costs to organizations (L'uba, 2016; Tabassum, 2011). While it is only normal that employees exit organizations from time to time due to voluntary and involuntary actions of appointment, retrenchment, retirement, temporary or permanent incapacitation, and death. Organizations that aim to be successful need to be proactive with the attraction of qualified persons to fill positions as they become vacant (Lawal, 2000; Peretomode and Peretomode 2001; Yaseen, 2015).

Job recruitment is conceptually defined as a process of finding and hiring the most qualified candidates for job openings in a cost-effective and timely manner (Omolawal and Okafor, 2016). There are two known types of recruitment, internal and external recruitment. Internal recruitment relates to identifying and attracting applicants among individuals already holding job positions within an organization and it could be in form of promotions, transfers, or deployments according to Kumari (2012). Internal recruitment is deemed to provide the benefits of strengthening existing employer-employee bonds, reducing hiring and training costs that would have been otherwise invested in new entrants, eliminating the costs associated with job posts and advertisements, and providing an opportunity for career progression and development which ultimately drives employee engagement and retention (Omisore and Okofu, 2014; CIPD, 2016). The most important benefit however seems to be guaranteed productivity and job performance since management is familiar with the applicant's capability and competence over the years as against the gamble recruitment errors associated with external recruitment. Internal recruitment also has its disadvantages. An example is a situation that leads to candidates lobbying since they know the key decision-makers, such practices can influence prejudice in the recruitment process or give rise to acts of Godfatherism. Other drawbacks include existing employees not possessing requisite skills for vacant jobs (Adeola and Adebisi, 2016; Olatunji and Ugoji, 2013).

External recruitment refers to creating a pool of candidates who are willing and available to work for a particular organization from outside the organization. The common external recruitment methods used are advertisement in the national newspapers, trade unions, recruitment agencies, head-hunting, universities

and college job fairs, referral methods, etc. (Rahman, Islam and Khan, 2015; Omolawal, 2021). External recruitment has the perceived benefits of encouraging merit and being devoid of discrimination. A principle based on the premise that every applicant will have to compete by undergoing the rigorous and time-tested processes of selection since prospective employees have no existing links with the organization and. The challenges associated with external recruitment are high recruitment costs involved in advert placement; longer periods spent on orientation and induction activities, and the possible demoralizing effects and sabotage among internal members who may feel aggrieved by the idea of injecting fresh blood into the organization to oversee sensitive positions (Lawal, 2000).

2.2 The Nigerian Perspective

Nigeria by being the country with the largest population in Africa, with an estimate of about 200 million people, can be deemed to have an abundance of human resources. The nation is also rich in mineral resources which makes it a center of attraction to investors across the globe especially in those industries such as extractive and manufacturing. This is making the country gradually integrate into the global business environment. Globalization by demanding that organizations conform to global benchmarks has influenced Human Resources Management practices in Nigerian organizations in various ways (Fajana *et al*, 2011; Tiemo and Arubayi, 2012).

The Labour Act 1974 governs recruitment practice in Nigeria, and also the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 in its section 14 (3) states that the composition of the government and its agencies and the conduct of its affairs shall reflect the Federal Character of Nigeria and the need to promote national unity. This is to be achieved by ensuring that no predominance of persons from a few ethnic groups, states, or other sectional groups dominate the government or any of its agencies. The significance of this provision cannot be overemphasized. However, it is commonly misinterpreted to be a mere euphemism for balancing ethnic dichotomy (Ayoade, 2000; Fajana *et al*, 2011; Tiemo and Arubayi, 2012).

2.3 The Public and Private Sector in Nigeria

The public sector consists of governments and all publicly controlled entities that deliver public programs, goods, or services (Institute of Internal Auditors, 2011). Nigeria's public sector comprises several institutions serving various functions related to the provision of goods and services to citizens. However, in comparison with the private sector, the public sector places a premium on the realization and representation of public interests. Nigeria's public sector in the 1960s post-independence era was widely regarded as the pivot that would promote the socio-economic development of the country. However, the attributes of the

Nigerian public service today are low efficiency and profitability, and poor accounting and reporting systems (Haque, 2001).

The mainstay of the sector in Nigeria is the Nigerian Civil Service, which is characterized by guaranteed jobs, unclear mandates, and poor service delivery. Osemeke (2011) attributed the unclear mandates to the political connections of the NCS, he also put forth that the guaranteed jobs coupled with the unclear mandates are what has resulted in the huge and ever-increasing number of civil servants. Okonjo-Iweala and Osafo-Kwaoko (2007) posit that the poor delivery of the sector is a result of an overly huge staff count and poor remunerations. Lewis (1990) argued political and bureaucratic interference is responsible for decadence. Other characteristics of the sector are: poor incentives to workers, corruption, extravagance, inefficiency and is overly bureaucratic, that is, it is hierarchical and staffed mainly by permanent career officials. Also, promotion is largely based on seniority, and remuneration is fixed. Employee performance management is also done annually and is often in form of companywide annual performance evaluation (Tonwe 1998; Imaga 2003).

The Private Sector can be defined as a primary organizing concept for an economic venture in which private ownership is a key factor, where markets and competition drive production, and where exclusive enterprise and risk-taking sets activities in motion (Development Assistance Committee, 1994). Ajila and Awonusi (2004) posit the private sector is more effective than the public sector in Nigeria due to practices such a differential wage payment systems as incentives to increase production and to attract more experienced staff from rival organizations, and an openness to the adoption of new initiatives that characterize the private sector.

Private Sector organizations focus on profit-making and although they are sometimes hierarchical, they employ largely on merit. Incentives are motivated by efficiency and as such promotion and increase in remunerations are dependent on productivity (Osemeke, 2011). Employee performance is thus monitored frequently and on an individual basis rather than on a companywide annual performance evaluation. Also, unlike in the public sector where societal and political pressures have a key influence on decision making, the Nigerian private sector organizations largely rely on efficiency-based and economic indicators. Most private sector businesses especially those that are public limited liability companies are legally required to publish performances and balance sheets annually. These practices allow for accountability and foster smart decisions (Osemeke, 2011).

3. RECRUITMENT IN THE PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SECTOR

3.1 Overview of Recruitment in Nigeria's Public Sector

Before the 1988 reforms, the civil service in Nigeria was strictly organized based on British traditions and was apolitical, conservative, and bureaucratic, making it a rigid system (Adamolekun and Gboyega, 1979). It was the amalgamation of the northern and southern protectorates of 1914 which set forth a unified government structure in Nigeria that however marked the beginning of the Nigerian civil service (Olowu *et al.*, 1997). The system remained in place after independence and is still functioning today although it has been undergoing systemic reforms since Democratic governance took over from military rule on May 29, 1999. This is evidenced by the vesting of powers to appoint persons to offices in federal civil service on the Federal Civil Service Commission (FRSC) by the 1999 Constitution. This is coupled with the power to dismiss and exercise disciplinary powers over persons holding such office.

In the Nigerian federal civil phraseology, an appointment is synonymous with recruitment and is often determined by three main factors which are:

- The availability of vacancies declared by the ministerial and extra-ministerial departments. Such are publicized through advertisements
- The qualifications of the potential applicants. The specific qualifications and skills required for various categories are presented in the schemes of service (2000)
- The final factor is the principle of federal character which is a constitutional matter and very important factor aimed at ensuring an even representation of all states, ethnicity, and regions or sectional groups of the federation in the federal service. A Federal Character Commission was created in 1995 for this purpose (Olowu *et al.*, 1997; Baburu, 2003; Al-Gazali, 2006)

The Federal Character principle which is aimed at ensuring equality by giving the six geo-political zones equal chances of employment is however not usually strictly adhered to in reality and is menaced by personal interests, social class and ethnic influences, and undue interference of the political class which often leads to recruitment of incompetent staff (Fajana, 2009; Tiemo and Arubayi, 2012).

According to Baburu (2003) Appointments to the Federal Civil Service are made either through recruitment, transfer or secondment. Recruitment refers to the appointment of persons not already in the civil service, transfers involve the permanent release of officers from one scheduled service to another or within the same service while secondment refers to temporary release of an officer to the service of another government agency or international organization of which Nigeria belongs (FRN, 2000: Rule 0228; FRN, 1998). According to Yaro (2014), the categories in which direct appointment to the Public Service are: (a) As

trainee or pupil; (b) On probation in a pensionable post; (c) On non-pensionable contract to a non-pensionable post or against a pensionable post; and (d) On temporary basis. Regarding eligibility for appointment into the public service in Nigeria, prospective candidates must be at least sixteen (16) years of age, possess minimum qualifications as are specified from time to time, be certified by a government medical officer as sound in health and medically fit for the government service and possess a testimonial of good conduct from his last employer or if not previously employed, from the last school or college he/she attended (Yaro, 2014).

The Nigerian constitution empowers the commission to delegate its powers and functions to ensure its efficient functioning and guard against delays because of the crucial role the commission is expected to play being a regulatory authority of the federal civil service.

Some of the other peculiarities of the public service in Nigeria are that it is characterized by an aging workforce, highly unionized towards protecting employees' rights, recruitment is often done annually, little or no attention to workforce planning and audit strategies, and more emphasis on skills rather than positive attitude during the recruitment process. The public sector in Nigeria is also highly unionized in terms of organized labour. (Fajana *et al*, 2011; Tiemo and Arubayi, 2012).

Briggs (2007) also found that connections and informal contacts dominate the sources of recruitment in the Nigerian civil service, especially at the entry-level roles while internal recruitment is often biased and based more on seniority than merit principle. Recruitments are also sometimes conducted without development and utilization of job descriptions, and recruits are often placed in areas where they may lack competency despite the processes focusing more on job specifications.

3.3 Overview of Recruitment in Nigeria's Private Sector

Globalization and intensification of information technology have very much influenced recruitment practices in the private sector with most recruitment exercises now taking place online. This new trend which is common in sectors such as manufacturing, telecommunications, and banking gives room for sanity by reducing the barriers posed by risks associated with road travel as well as transportation costs. It however also has its drawbacks such as the pace of technological development in Nigeria (Omolawal, 2015; Adeyori and Fajebe, 2018). Outsourcing is another trend that globalization has necessitated in organizations. Outsourcing refers to the practice of delegating hiring functions to specialist firms to allow organizations to focus on their core areas of operations and more pressing issues (Omolawal and Okafor, 2016; Adeyori and Fajebe, 2018). Most private organizations today rely on the expertise of recruitment agencies to fill vacant positions. Some uncertified recruitment agencies have however been found to be

involved in the silly practice of extorting job applicants (Omolawal and Okafor, 2016), such corrupt practices are however not as rampant in the private sector especially when compared to the public sector.

While politics and personal influence are seen as the key challenges to effective recruitment in the public sector, challenges of effective recruitment in the private sector is mostly attributed to the falling standards of education in the country which is making it increasingly difficult to absorb qualified and highly competent graduates to satisfy the country's employment and industrial base. This is however a pointer to the relevance the private sector places on high entry requirements in terms of candidate competency. Discrimination, particularly based on age and sex also poses a challenge in private sector recruitment. A lot of Nigerian organizations are guilty of gender discrimination with male employees mostly occupying managerial positions, even in cases where it is obvious some women possess the necessary quality and qualifications (Tiemo and Arubayi, 2012).

Some other distinguishing features of private sector recruitments are; placement of recruits in their areas of core competency, use of detailed job descriptions and job specifications, recruitments are also only conducted on a need basis and when true vacancies exist. This is due to the constant workforce audit and workforce planning activities which is characteristic of private organizations (Briggs, 2007).

4.0 DISCUSSION

The overview of the recruitment practices in the public and private sectors of Nigeria as narrated in the previous chapter shows the similarities and differences in the sectors. It revealed recruitment in the public sector has a statutory flavor and certain statutory obligations have to be met such as the Federal Character principle to ensure equity and equality. Although in reality the goal of equity and fairness is hardly achieved as the principle has been menaced by misuse in form of personal interests, nepotism, and ethnic influences by the political and ruling class, this has led to the recruitment of non-qualified personnel in place of merit, a contributing factor to the inefficiency, mediocrity and low productivity crippling the Nigerian public service. The private sector on the other hand operates more flexibly with no rigid rules and can apply the global best practices at will. Thus, it can recruit more credible staff as a result of the objective and well-planned recruitment processes. This is not to say politics and personal influence do not play a role in the private sector, but the level of inadequacy in the public sector is more observable.

The practices of corruption, bias, and the likes associated with public service recruitment are due to the increasing pressures from applicants on the influential people at the helm of affairs at the ministries and extra-ministerial departments that recruitment activities are often delegated to. This makes the delegation

of the activities of the federal civil service to these agencies also a major source of the problem as it leads to non-adherence to recruitment policies and procedures.

Recruitment in the private sector in recent years is mostly computer-based and through smart processes of modern software tools which comes with the benefit of helping to do away with challenges of transportation costs and road travels for candidates. The public sector on the other hand is usually overly bureaucratic in its dealings and recruitment processes often involve submitting several copies of various credentials in hard copies to various ministries and departments for the recruitment process. The pressures applicants place on the influential contacts is as a result of the employment in the sector being perceived as flexible, with lots of civil servants known to be involved in a side business and the permanence nature of the pensionable employment which is not as common in the private sector. These pressures put recruiting authorities under the pressure to recruit without due recourse to workforce planning, making the system have excess and unproductive staff.

Another key difference between both sectors is that in the public service, for the lower and/or entry-level roles which are usually external, recruitment sources are mostly through connections and informal contacts. For the higher ranking roles, mostly internal recruitment is often very biased and often based on seniority rather than merit. This is very unlike the private sector in which promotion and ascension are based on a track record of performances, competency, and exposure on the job. Also, the conduct of recruitment exercises without the development and utilization of job descriptions is a serious problem facing the civil service as it deprives the commission of adequate information for objective recruitment decisions and makes it difficult to specify tasks to be performed. This is why there are many civil servants without defined duties and thus giving the perception of flexibility in the system. This is very much unlike the private sector.

The private sector asides from developing job descriptions and job specifications to be utilized for recruitments exercises also establish relatively high staff requirements, resulting in the acquisition of better quality staff compared to the public sector. This has contributed to the increasing levels by which incompetent candidates are consistently placing pressures for employment in the public sector since personnel requirements are lower and there is high utilization of informal sources of recruitment. This may explain why it is tough to find top first-class graduates and other highly competent professionals in civil service today. The belief is that the system which used to recruit the very best University graduates and professionals, leaving the other less able to other sectors of the economy, is now mediocre. The private sector business is currently doing much better with the attraction, recruitment, and retention of top talent. Talents are also usually placed in their areas of competency in the private sector organizations unlike in

public service where anything goes are officers often find themselves in areas where they lack proficiency. This explains why the private sector in Nigeria is more productive than the public sector.

The similarities both sectors share is are that they both struggle to manage and maintain diversity and equality effectively especially with discrimination and denial of opportunities based on gender, religion and religion. The delegation of recruitment functions through outsourcing to specialized recruitment agencies, which globalization has brought to the limelight, is also another area of similarity.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The paper finds that while both sectors share the similarities of struggling to manage equality issues and effectively the strength of Nigeria's cultural and religious diversity to advance organizational goals, the practice of delegating recruitment functions to specialized recruiting agencies and the associated ills is also gaining traction in both sectors. Differences, however, exist in the areas of recruitment sources especially at the entry-level which is mostly formal in the private and informal in the public, mostly involving connections and informal contacts. Adoption of ICT tools and smart recruitment processes, development and utilization of job descriptions, high entry requirements, and placement of recruits in their areas of core competencies are also rampant in private sector recruitment. Making it more effective with the recruitment of choice talents.

It is important to curb the identified recruitment problems as the recruitment process is the bedrock upon which the success of any organization is built as established in the debut chapter, the paper thus recommends:

- Managers in both sectors should make it a responsibility to ensure principles of equity and fairness are strictly adhered to in recruitment processes while paying keen attention to the protection of the individuals and vulnerable groups from discriminatory practices menacing the Nigerian workplace. The federal government also needs to review the Federal Character principle if it is to perform its initial focus of ensuring fairness and equity by applying it only at the lowest levels while other grade levels should be strictly on merit, or otherwise wipe it out of the constitution to abate the indiscipline, inefficiency, and incompetence among the sector's workforce
- Organizations both private and public should ensure only competent and professional human resources practitioners who have a code of conduct to abide by are engaged to conduct recruitment

activities on their behalf. This will also aid the use of reliable and valid recruitment models that predict job success

- The public sector should take a cue from the private and carry out recruitment exercises only based on human resources needs, supported by well-defined job descriptions to avoid excess of staff with no directions on how to proceed in the sector. The positive attitude of candidates should also be considered as against just emphasizing job specifications
- With the high level of unionization in the public sector, labour unions in the sector can use their strong profiles to discuss and bring about a change a change in form of effective recruitment processes as against the usual bread and butter issues that are always at the forefront of negotiations. This itself will enhance managements' perception of these unions statuses and will portray them as being rational and credible
- The federal government also needs to propagate employment regulations that will guarantee job security in private sector to reduce the pressures for employment in the public sector while discouraging use of public office for personal gains by the informal contacts relied on in its recruiting agencies

Finally, rewards and compensations of public service personnel should be increased to be at par with or close to that of their counterparts in the private sector in order to be able to attract more competent applicants and to reduce the high rate of turnover at the higher levels of the service.

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